

Data for voice synthesis of Livonian

Version 1

Description

The Data Management Plan is developed in the framework of the Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007), grant project "Improving access to a critically under-resourced language: AI-based approaches for producing and obtaining Livonian content" (LU-BA-PA-2024/1-0056). Data is collected in order to create speech synthesis for Livonian and lay the ground for development of speech recognition.

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

Recovery and Resilience Facility
project "Internal and External
Consolidation of the University
of Latvia"
(No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007).

Researchers

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Organizations

University of Latvia Livonian Institute

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Data for voice synthesis of Livonian](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#) | [EC](#)

Grants: [Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" \(No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007\)](#).

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date:

4. Templates

Descriptions

Livonian voice data

Collection of voice data for Latvia's indigenous Livonian language. Purpose of collection is to create Livonian speech synthesis and lay a base for the creation of speech synthesis. Collection of data consists of aligned voice and text data (words, sentences, whole texts samples) in multiple voices covering time period from 1960s until today. Data collection is ongoing and data will be available after 02.2026.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Textual data
- Other

voice

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- MP3
- Others

wav

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

TB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

Yes

1.1.7 If Yes, please indicate what data set are you re-using?

- Estonian Language Institute
- University of Tartu

id: null, Type: null

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers of Livonian, builders of speech synthesis

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Valts Ernštreits

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Some data may contain sensitive information.

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

Privacy constraints

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